

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Triallylamine by Alkaline Potassium Hexacyanoferrate(III)

M. M. AL-SUBU

Department of Chemistry, An-Najah University, Nablus, West Bank, Via Israel

Manuscript received 3 August 1989, revised 15 January 1990, accepted 21 November 1990

Kinetics of the oxidation of triallylamine by hexacyanoferrate(III) in alkaline medium have been studied. The rate is independent of the concentration of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$, while the orders in [triallylamine] and $[\text{OH}^-]$ are nearly unity and 0.33 respectively. The rate of the reaction is not retarded by added $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$ ions. The effects of ionic strength varying cations and anions of added salts, solvent composition and temperature on the reaction rate are reported. A suitable mechanism has been proposed

KINETICS and mechanism of oxidation of tertiary amines by hexacyanoferrate(III) (a one-electron oxidant) have been studied extensively¹. It has been suggested that the oxidation proceeds through equations (1) - (4),

It was also suggested that the principal rate-controlling step in the oxidation was an electron-abstraction (equation 1) rather than the deprotonation of the amine cation (equation 2). The above mechanism is a subject of continuing interest. It was, therefore, decided to examine the oxidation of triallylamine by hexacyanoferrate(III). The results of the kinetic investigation of this reaction in alkaline buffer solution containing ethanol (60%, v/v) are reported here.

Experimental

Triallylamine (Virginia Chemicals) was refluxed and fractionated over solid KOH prior to its use. All other chemicals (E. Merck) were used as such. Buffers were prepared from NaOH and KCl in 60% (v/v) ethanol. Double-distilled water was used throughout.

Stoichiometry: Reaction mixtures containing five-fold excess of hexacyanoferrate(III) over triallylamine were allowed to react in ethanol-water (60%, v/v) at room temperature and at constant pH. The left-over hexacyanoferrate(III) was analysed spectrophotometrically. The results gave 1 : 2 stoichiometry for triallylamine-hexacyanoferrate(III).

Kinetics: The kinetic studies were conducted by monitoring the absorbance of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ (at 414 nm) vs time. The required volumes of triallylamine and hexacyanoferrate(III) (stock solutions)

were dissolved separately in portions of the buffer. Sodium chloride was added to keep a constant ionic strength. The total volume of the reaction mixture was kept constant. The contents of the two flasks were mixed, shaken and continuous measurement of the absorbance vs time was made until at least 60% reaction was complete. In a similar manner but adjusting the volume of buffer solution to keep a constant volume, the effects of added hexacyanoferrate(II) and other salts on the reaction rate were studied separately.

All spectra were recorded using a SP8-100 ultraviolet spectrophotometer. pH measurements were made on a Fisher Accumet 230A pH meter.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry: On the basis of the results of experiments performed to establish the stoichiometry of the $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ oxidation of triallylamine at alkaline pH, the molar ratio of triallylamine- $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ used was 1 : 2. Diallylamine and the polymer of acrylaldehyde were identified qualitatively as the oxidation products. Thus the overall reaction can be written as

The oxidation of triallylamine by $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ was investigated at several initial [reactants]. It was observed that initial rate values are constant at all $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]$ (Table 1), suggesting that the rate of reaction is independent on hexacyanoferrate(III) concentration. The plot of \log [initial rate] against \log [triallylamine] was linear with a slope of approximately unity, thus establishing a first order dependence in triallylamine concentration (Fig. 1). The results of the effect of changing pH of the reaction medium on the reaction rate indicate that the order of the reaction with respect to the hydroxide ion concentration is a fraction of about 1/3 (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Plot of $-\log [\text{Initial rate}]$ vs $\log [\text{Triallylamine}]$ at 25° ; $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $\text{pH} = 13.0$, $\mu = 0.1$.

Fig. 2. Plot of $-\log [\text{Initial rate}]$ vs pOH at 20° ; $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Triallylamine}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ M}$, $\mu = 0.1$.

$[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] (\times 10^3 \text{ M})$	0.50	0.70	1.00	1.30	1.50
Initial rate ($\times 10^3 \text{ M s}^{-1}$)	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.05	1.95

Variations in the ionic strength of the reaction medium using NaCl showed a positive salt effect on the rate of the reaction (Fig. 3). Varying the anion by carrying out the reaction in the presence of KF,

Fig. 3. Plot of k_{obs} vs $[\text{NaCl}]$ at 31° ; $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Triallylamine}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ M}$.

KBr, KI and KNO_3 , one at a time, and the addition of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ did not have any significant effect on rate of the reaction (Table 2). However, changing the salt cation by using NH_4Cl , NaCl and KCl, the rate was enhanced according to the order: $\text{Na}^+ \gg \text{K}^+ \gg \text{NH}_4^+$ (Table 3).

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF SALTS OF DIFFERENT ANIONS ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION OF TRIALLYLAMINE

$[\text{Amine}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Salt}] = 6.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$, $\text{pH} = 13.6$, $\text{Temp.} = 32^\circ$

Salt	Initial rate $\times 10^3 \text{ M s}^{-1}$
KF	2.86
KBr	2.84
KI	2.82
KNO_3	2.82

The reaction of triallylamine with $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ was carried out at different concentrations of ethanol (60, 65, 70 and 75%, v/v). The results showed no

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF SALTS OF DIFFERENT CATIONS ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION OF TRIALLYLAMINE

[Amine] = 2.0×10^{-3} M, [Fe(CN)₆³⁻] = 1.0×10^{-3} M, [Salt] = 6.0×10^{-2} M, pH = 13.6, Temp. = 28°

Salt	Initial rate $\times 10^3$ M s ⁻¹
NH ₄ Cl	0.75
KCl	2.35
NaCl	2.70

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF VARYING AMOUNT OF ETHANOL IN REACTION MEDIUM ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION OF TRIALLYLAMINE

[Amine] = 2.0×10^{-3} M, [Fe(CN)₆³⁻] = 1.0×10^{-3} M, pH = 13.6, $\mu = 0.1$, Temp. = 29°

Ethanol % (v/v)	Initial rate $\times 10^3$ M s ⁻¹
60	2.20
65	2.22
70	2.20
75	2.22

significant change on the rate of the reaction (Table 4).

The reaction rate was enhanced by an increase in the temperature, and the activation energy and thermodynamic parameters were evaluated (Table 5).

TABLE 5—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR THE OXIDATION OF TRIALLYLAMINE

E _a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	66.53
ΔH [‡] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	64.04
ΔS [‡] (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-28.03
ΔG [‡] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	55.66
A(s ⁻¹)	2.06×10^{11}

One mole of triallylamine was oxidised by two moles of alkaline² hexacyanoferrate(III) to produce diallylamine and the polymer of acrylaldehyde. The observed stoichiometry is the same as that reported for the oxidation of tertiary amines by hexacyanoferrate(III)¹. The kinetics showed that the reaction is first order in triallylamine and 1/3 in the hydroxide ion concentration but independent of [Fe(CN)₆³⁻]. Thus, the abstraction of the first electron is not likely to be involved in the rate-determining step. Instead, the rate-determining step might involve either the hydrogen abstraction process (equation 2) similar to other oxidations of some tertiary amines² or the abstraction of the second electron (equation 3). The observed cationic salt effect in our results, though not remarkable (Table 3), favours equation (3) rather than equation (2) as cations are known to act as bridges for electron transfer. Similar evidence for equation (3) can be deduced from the positive salt-effect obtained experimentally by addition of different concentrations of NaCl (Fig. 3). A third evidence on equation (3) can be seen from the effect of the type of anion on the rate of the reaction. Changing

the anion of the added salt from F⁻ to Br⁻ to I⁻ to NO₃⁻ has no effect on the reaction rate (Table 2). Br⁻, I⁻ or NO₃⁻ are very weak bases or neutral, and changing one by the other is not expected to cause a significant change on the rate of abstraction of a proton as found experimentally. But if the abstraction of a proton is indeed the rate-controlling step, addition of F⁻ is expected to enhance the rate. However, such effect was not observed in the present case. Finally, the negligible effect of the dielectric constant of the medium on the reaction rate, as can be seen from the unchanged rate upon increasing the concentration of ethanol, supports equation (2) as much as it does for equation (3). Apparently, the rate-determining step involves the abstraction of the second electron rather than any of the other steps in the reaction.

In the light of the results, the following mechanism (equations 6–9) may be proposed,

The formation of the amine cation radical (I) by one-electron transfer to hexacyanoferrate(III) (equation 6) occurs in the fast step. The amine radical cation (I) deprotonates at the α-carbon, and either (II) or (III) is formed (equations 7a and 7b respectively). Species (II) or (III) is further oxidised by another Fe(CN)₆³⁻ to the ammonium salt (IV) (equations 8a and 8b respectively), which hydrolyses to the dealkylated amine (diallylamine) and the carbonyl compound (polymer of acrylaldehyde)

(equation 9). The formation of α -amine radical (II) is well-established in the literature¹. The oxidation of the α -carbon of a trialkylamine is also known and analogous to reactions occurring between several other oxidants and a variety of tertiary amines, especially those containing the benzyl group³.

The above mechanism enables us to derive the rate equation as follows,

$$\text{Rate} = k_3 [\text{II}] [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] \quad (9)$$

Applying steady state assumption for [II],

$$[\text{II}] = k_2 [\text{I}] / k_3 [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] \quad (10)$$

$$\text{but, } [\text{I}] = K[(\text{C}_3\text{H}_5)_3\text{N}][\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] / [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}] \quad (11)$$

Substituting equation (11) and equation (10),

$$[\text{II}] = Kk_2[(\text{C}_3\text{H}_5)_3\text{N}] / k_3 [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}] \quad (12)$$

Substituting equation (12) in equation (9),

$$\text{Rate} = Kk_2[(\text{C}_3\text{H}_5)_3\text{N}] \frac{[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}]} \quad (13)$$

Since the first step in the proposed mechanism is fast and reversible, therefore $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] / [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}]$ is constant, and it could be incorporated into the overall rate constant,

$$\text{Rate} = k_{\text{obs}} [(\text{C}_3\text{H}_5)_3\text{N}] \quad (14)$$

$$\text{where, } k_{\text{obs}} = Kk_2[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] / [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}] \quad (15)$$

The derived rate law explains the zero order rate observed for hexacyanoferrate(III).

The relatively low values of E_a and ΔH^\ddagger might be due to the resonance stabilisation of (II) and (IV) by the allyl groups.

Acknowledgement

The author is grateful to professor H. H. Sisler for his valuable comments and thankful to N.C.C. Nablu for printing the manuscript.

References

1. H. B. HENBEST and R. PATTON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 3557; L. A. HULL, G. T. DAVIS and D. H. ROSENBLATT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 6247; C. A. AUDREH and J. R. LINDSAY SMITH, *J. Chem. Soc. (B)*, 1970, 1280; 1971, 1745; J. R. LINDSAY SMITH and L. A. V. MEAD, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1973, 206; 1976, 1172; K. S. SHUKLA, P. C. MATHUR and O. P. BANSAL, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 1301.
2. N. L. WEINBERG and H. R. WEINBERG, *Chem. Rev.*, 1968, **68**, 449; C. K. MANN and K. K. BAMES, "Electrochemical Reactions in Non-Aqueous Systems", Marcel Dekker, New York, 1970; L. C. PORTIS, V. V. BHAT and C. J. MANN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1970, **35**, 2175; B. L. LAUBE, M. R. ASIRVATHAM and C. K. MANN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1977, **42**, 670; Y. L. CHOW, W. G. DANEN, S. F. NELSON and D. H. ROSENBLATT, *Chem. Rev.*, 1978, **78**, 243.
3. D. H. ROSENBLATT, A. J. HAYFR, Jr., B. L. HARRISON, R. A. STREAY and K. A. MOORE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **28**, 2790; D. H. ROSENBLATT, L. A. HULL, D. C. DELUCA, G. T. DAVIS, R. C. WEGLEIN and H. K. R. WILLIAMS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 1158; L. A. HULL, G. T. DAVIS, D. H. ROSENBLATT, H. K. R. WILLIAMS and R. C. WAGLEIN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 1163.